

Indigenous traditional knowledge and scientific validation of selected plant of North East India

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Natural Product Chemistry is one of the major areas of research and development in today's world. The role and contributions of indigenous traditional knowledge and natural products chemistry in advancements of the Chemical, physical and biological sciences, its interdisciplinary domains, and emerging of new avenues by providing novel applications, comprehensive understanding, broad perspective are very significant. Indigenous traditional knowledge also involves with all selected plant from time immemorial which has different therapeutic value. So, details scientific validation must need for future mankind. The developmental prospects in bio-medical, health, nutrition, and other interrelated sciences along with some of the emerging trends in the subject area are also discussed as part of the current research of the basic and core developments, innovation in techniques, advances in methodology, and possible applications with their effects on the sciences in general and natural products chemistry in particular. Concerning all these aspects we have selected a few medicinal and aromatic plant of North East India for study of its indigenous traditional knowledge and evaluation of its therapeutic value. Accordingly, the details report of our study of the specific medicinal and aromatic plant will be discussed.